

FISCAL POLICY AND INDUSTRIAL SECTOR OUTPUT IN NIGERIA

CORDILIA IKHANE

MSc Student, Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Email: ikhanec@babcock.edu.ng (+2348038760196)

ROWLAND TOCHUKWU OBIAKOR

Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Email: obiakort@babcock.edu.ng (+2348060792785)

OVIKUOMAGBE OYEDELE

Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Email: oyedelev@babcock.edu.ng (+2348028436256) (Corresponding Author)

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of fiscal policy on output from the industrial sector in Nigeria. Using data from the World Development Indicators (2024) and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2023) from 1985 to 2023. The study employed the autoregressive distributed lag model and the weighted least square estimator. The results showed that only the public expenditure component of fiscal policy significantly determined industrial sector output and although public recurrent expenditure had a positive effect, public capital expenditure had a reduction effect. Public revenue and public external debt were not significant. Therefore, government consumption spendings in the form of recurrent expenditure should patronize domestically produced goods in order to sustain the positive effect. Public capital expenditure should intentionally provide the basic infrastructures that reduce the cost of doing business in the industrial sector. There is also the need to substantially increase the proportion of revenue and debts specifically used by the government to create an enabling environment for investors in the industrial sector to thrive and expand.

Keywords: Output, Industrial sector, Fiscal policy, Nigeria

JEL Classification: H2, H3, O4

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrialization is a deliberate effort to promote the establishment and expansion of industries in a particular location or country. The industrial sector is essential for economic development as it creates employment and provides a ready market for resources from the agricultural sector especially in the food industry.

Industrial sector output is the total value of goods and services produced by industries within a country over a specific period of time. Based on the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2024), the industrial sector is made up of five major sub-sectors. The first is mining and quarrying; the second sub-sector is manufacturing while electricity, gas, steam and air conditioner make up the third sub-sector. Water supply, sewage and waste management constitute the fourth subsector. Construction is the fifth sub-sector. Manufacturing, mining, and construction are crucial to Nigeria's economic diversification. The sector has traditionally promoted sustainable economic growth and reduced oil revenue dependence. However, based on the CBN Economic Report (2024), domestic economic activity contracted in October 2024 attributed to weakening demand. The Composite purchasing managers' index (PMI) declined at 49.6 index points in October 2024 from 50.5 index points in the preceding month. The

decline was driven, mainly, by reduced output in the industry and services sector. The industry sector PMI decreased to 49.3 index points from 49.7 index points recorded in preceding month, remaining below the expansion threshold (CBN Economic Report, 2024).

Nigeria still lags behind especially when it comes to meeting up with the criteria of being called an industrialized nation. Many industries for instance in the manufacturing sector start production but after sometime close down due to challenges. Therefore the sustainable development of industries is pertinent. Several studies have considered the effect of fiscal policy on output but considered total output (Olaniyi *et al.*, 2024, Acikgoz & Cinar 2017, Choi & Son 2016, Eller *et al.* 2016, Zagler & Dumecker 2003, Easterly & Rebelo 1993). However, a specific examination of output from the industrial sector is important for providing policies that address the sector's unique challenges. Some studies have examined the effect of fiscal policy on industrial output but they considered the effect of only one aspect of fiscal policy. For instance, Oshota (2023) considered the effect of only one aspect of fiscal policy which is government spending. Oladipo *et al.* (2023) considered the effect of corporate income tax and government capital expenditures on the mining and quarrying sector. Others include Ozuzu & Isukul (2021), Falade & Oladiran (2015) and Nwanne (2015). There is the need to examine the effect of various components of fiscal policy in order to determine the differences in how they drive industrial output growth. This study therefore examined the effect of fiscal policy on output from the industrial sector in Nigeria. It considered the effect of fiscal policy using three components, which are revenue, expenditure and debt in order to determine their differential effects. The rest of the paper includes section 2 – literature review, section 3 – the methodology, section 4 – results and discussion of findings, and section 5 – conclusion and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The Solow (1956) output growth theory states that output is determined by input such as capital and labour. Solow (1956) developed an alternative model to the Harrod-Domar line of thought without its crucial assumption of fixed proportions in production. Solow (1956) postulated a continuous production function linking output to the inputs of capital and labour which are substitutable. Harrod (1939) and Domar (1946) modelled output as a function of capital only and explores the relationship between savings, investment and economic growth. They maintained that an increase in investment leads to an increase in output.

2.2 Empirical Literature

The industrial sector, characterized by its capital-intensive nature, is highly responsive to macroeconomic policies, particularly fiscal measures. Tkalec and Vizek (2009) examined the impact of macroeconomic policies on manufacturing production in Croatia. The analysis was conducted using quarterly data from 1998 to 2008. The estimated method used was ordinary least squares approach. The results showed that restrictive monetary policy led to the contraction of manufacturing output. The results for exchange rate revealed that exchange rate depreciation boosts output in industries characterized by low and medium technological intensity but the opposite was true for industries requiring a high or medium level of technological intensity.

Joshua-Gyang (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing industrial sector in Nigeria from 1987 to 2022. The estimation method used was the auto-regressive distributed lag. Government recurrent expenditures in Nigeria had a positive and significant effect on manufacturing industrial sector output in Nigeria. While, non-oil taxation had a positive and insignificant effect on manufacturing industrial sector output and the other hand,

oil taxation was found to negative and significant effect on manufacturing industrial sector output. Also, the result revealed that public external debt had a negative and insignificant effect on manufacturing industrial sector output while public domestic debt was found to have a positive and significant effect on manufacturing industrial sector output.

Mohammed (2024) examined the effect of public debt and government expenditure on industrial sector output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. The estimation method used was the autoregressive distributed lag model. The study found that domestic debt and external debt had a negative and significant effect on industrial sector performance but with a low magnitude, capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure are also affecting the sector performance but not adequate. Exchange rate, domestic debt and capital expenditure had negative and significant effect on industrial sector output.

Umoh and Effiong (2013) examined the effect of trade openness on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria from 1970 to 2008. The study employed the autoregressive distributed lag estimator. The study found out that in the long run, interest rate had a negative and significant effect on manufacturing sector. Trade openness and exchange rate had a positive and significant effect. Omarkhanlen *et al.* (2021) examined the effect of government revenue on sustainable industrial sector output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 using the vector error correction model. The study revealed that government revenue had a positive and insignificant effect on industrial sector output, capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect on industrial sector output. Gross fixed capital formation also had a negative and significant.

Ozuzu and Isukul (2021) examined the effect of government expenditure on industrial sector output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2015. The estimation method used was the vector error correction model and the study found that government capital expenditure, tax and the monetary policy rate had positive and significant effects on industrial sector output.

Kpagih *et al.* (2022) investigated the effect of the external sector on manufacturing sector in Nigeria from 1981 to 2019. The estimation method used was the autoregressive distributed lag model. The result showed that exchange and trade openness had a negative effect on manufacturing sector output.

Obi *et al.* (2020) investigated the impact of foreign direct investment on industrial output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 using the error correction mechanism. The findings revealed that foreign direct investment had a positive and insignificant impact on industrial growth. Also, financial institutions (proxied by credit to private sector) had no significant impact on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. More so, institutional quality (proxies by corruption perception index) had an insignificant effect on foreign direct investment. Foreign direct investment had a negative and insignificant effect on domestic investment (proxies by gross national private capital formation). The study recommends, among other things, that the government should, through the ministry of trade and investment enact and reform extant laws and policies that could boost the ease of doing business index for Nigeria. This could be done by reinvigorating investment-attracting mechanisms in the less invested sectors of the economy such as the mining and quarrying sector.

Eze (2014) examined the effect of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria from 1990 to 2010. The estimation method used was the error correction analysis and the ordinary least square model. The result showed that there is a long-run relationship between fiscal policy and manufacturing sector output and government expenditure had a positive and significant effect.

Effiong *et al.* (2024) examined the effect of fiscal policy (government spending and taxation) and interest rates on Nigeria's manufacturing sector from 1981 to 2021. The study employed the ARDL model. The findings revealed that, in the short term, government expenditure and its one-period lag negatively and significantly impacted manufacturing sector performance; value added tax positively and significantly influenced manufacturing sector performance,

while its one-period lag negatively and significantly affected it; and interest rate positively and significantly impacted manufacturing sector performance. Ultimately, government expenditure had a negative albeit negligible impact on the performance of the manufacturing sector, whereas value-added tax and interest rates have a positive and large influence. In the disaggregated model, recurrent expenditure has a negative and significant impact; capital expenditure has a positive and significant impact; value added tax has a negative and significant impact; and interest rate had a positive and significant influence on the performance of the manufacturing sector.

Uffie and Aghanenu (2019) examined the effect of fiscal variables on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria from 1981 to 2016. The estimation method used was the ARDL model. The study showed that fiscal policy has both short-run and long-run impacts on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. Specifically, government expenditure has positive significant impact on manufacturing output while company income tax dampened output owing to multiplicity of taxes.

Nwanne (2015) examined the effect of governmental capital expenditure on the output of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria with quantitative time-series data and multiple regression techniques. The co-integration test indicated a long-term relationship between the explained and explanatory factors. The analysis indicated that government capital expenditure on the road network and communication significantly influences manufacturing sector production, whereas government capital spending on power had a negligible effect on manufacturing sector output.

Falade and Oladiran (2015) examined the effect of government expenditure on manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The study considered both capital and recurrent expenditure. The study utilised time-series data spanning from 1970 to 2013. The estimated method used was Johansen cointegration approach. The result showed that the effect of government capital expenditure on manufacturing output had a negative and significant effect on manufacturing output sector, while the second lagged effect on manufacturing output was positive and significance. The effect of recurrent expenditure, nominal income series, real income series, interest rate and exchange rate had a negative and significant effect on manufacturing sector output

Arikpo *et al.* (2017) examined the effect of fiscal policy on the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria from 1982 to 2014. The estimation method used was ordinary least square multiple regression technique. The study showed that the government revenue was not significant but government expenditure was significant. Ighoroje and Akpokerere (2021) examined the effect fiscal policy on industrial sector output in Nigeria from 1987 to 2019 by employing the error correction model. The results showed that fiscal policy has a long run and short run effect on industry sector output. The specific results evidenced that government expenditure and budget deficit have significant positive impact on industry sector output in Nigeria; while tax revenue had a positive but insignificant effect on industry sector output in Nigeria.

Ogu & Kem (2020) assessed the impact of tax collection on the performance of Nigeria's manufacturing sector from 1981 to 2018. The study used the ordinary least squares regression analysis. The results indicated that the aggregate tax contributions from corporations, taxes on petroleum products, customs duties, and excise taxes, alongside the capacity utilisation of the manufacturing sector, exhibit a significant correlation with the performance of the manufacturing sector. However, when assessed independently, corporate taxes and taxes on petroleum products demonstrate a positive impact but lack a significant relationship with manufacturing sector performance. In contrast, taxes levied on the import and export of specific goods and services, as well as capacity utilisation, revealed both a positive impact and a significant relationship with the output of the industrial sector.

Olawale *et al.* (2017) examined the effect of governmental financial development on manufacturing sector output from 1970 to 2014. The estimation method used was the ARDL approach. The study found that government expenditure had a positive but little effect on manufacturing sector production.

Eze *et al.* (2019) examined the effect of foreign direct investment on manufacturing sector output growth in Nigeria for the period 1970 to 2016. The estimation method used was the ordinary least squares and Granger causality test. The study revealed that there is a long run relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and manufacturing sector output growth but it was insignificant. Granger causality result shows that there is a unidirectional causality from foreign direct investment to manufacturing sector output. Oyediran and Olajide (2024) found an insignificant effect of FDI on manufacturing capacity utilization in Nigeria, although it had a positive and significant effect on the GDP and gross capital formation.

Aiyedogbon *et al.* (2023) investigated the effect of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria between 1986 and 2021. The estimation method used was the fully modified ordinary least square method. The result showed that fiscal policy strategies significantly bolster the output of the manufacturing sector output. Imide (2019) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector of Nigeria from 1980 to 2017. The estimation method used was the ordinary least squares. The study revealed that government expenditure had a positive relationship with the index of the manufacturing sector while federal government domestic debt outstanding had a negative linear relationship with the index of the manufacturing sector. Victor and Roman (2017) analyzed the effect of fiscal policy on agriculture and industry in Ukraine from 2001 to 2016. The estimation method used was the SVAR model. The results showed that government spending had a positive effect on both agricultural production and industrial output, while an increase in government revenue is of the same expansionary impact for the latter only. Neoh and Lai (2021) examined the effect of trade openness on manufacturing sector output in Malaysia from 1981 to 2016 using the autoregressive distributed lag model. The results revealed that the effect of both instantaneous and the jointly dynamic effect of the percentage change in trade openness on manufacturing production growth in Malaysia were positive and significant. However, the effects of the percentage change in exchange rate and percentage change in average lending rate were insignificant. Economic crisis had a negative and significant impact on Malaysian manufacturing production growth.

Yalah and Ogoun (2023) investigated the effect of gross fixed capital formation on industrial sector output in Nigeria from 2001 to 2021. Using the Pearson correlation analysis, the study found that gross fixed capital formation had no correlation with industrial growth. Oshota (2023) examined the effect of fiscal policy on sectoral output growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2021. Using the autoregressive distributed lag model, the study found that total government expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the manufacturing sector in both the short run and long run. However, the effect was negative and significant for agriculture, building and construction, mining and service sector outputs in the long run but in the short run, agriculture and mining sector output increased. The study considered only one aspect of fiscal policy which is government spending. Oladipo *et al.* (2023) investigated the effect of fiscal policy on the development of the industrial sector in Nigeria from 1986 to 2021. Corporate income tax had a negative but insignificant effect while government capital expenditures on the mining and quarrying sector had a positive effect on solid minerals output in both the short and long run. The exchange rate was insignificant. Aghion *et al.* (2011) investigated whether differences in fiscal policy cyclicality across countries and in financial constraints across industries can account for cross country cross industry growth differences. Industry growth was measured using the average annual growth rate of labour productivity and or real value

added in the industry. Interacting credit constrains and the cyclicity of fiscal policy, the study found that having a more countercyclical fiscal policy enhances output and productivity growth more in industries that are facing more financial constraints. Popiel (2020) found no systematic relationship between fiscal policy uncertainty and output in the United States. Tahir *et al.* (2019) investigated the effect of trade openness on three different sectors of the economy such as the industrial, agriculture and service sectors for the case of developing countries. The study employed the fixed effect estimator, the feasible generalized least squares and the generalized method of moment estimator. Trade openness and employment had a positive effect on the industrial and agricultural sectors but it reduced output from the service sector. Human capital had a negative effect on all sectors while domestic credit to the private sector had a positive effect on the industrial and service sectors but an adverse effect on agriculture.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework and Model Specification

This study is based on the Solow (1956) output growth theory, which states that output is determined by input such as capital and labour. The Solow (1956) theory developed an alternative model to the Harrod-Domar line of thought without its crucial assumption of fixed proportions in production. Solow (1956) postulated a continuous production function linking output to the inputs of capital and labour which are substitutable. This study measured capital and labour using the gross fixed capital formation and labour force participation rate respectively.

The model is presented as:

$$Y = f(\text{GFC}, \text{LFP}) \tag{1}$$

This study examined the effect of fiscal policy on sectoral output in Nigeria. The study considered the effect of fiscal policy. Fiscal policy was measured using public revenue, public capital expenditure and public debt. Public revenue was decomposed into oil revenue and non-oil revenue. Public expenditure was decomposed into recurrent and capital expenditure. Public debt was decomposed into public external debt and public domestic debt. The model therefore becomes:

$$Y = f(\text{GFC}, \text{LFP}, \text{OR}, \text{NOR}, \text{PRE}, \text{PCE}, \text{PDD}, \text{PED}) \tag{2}$$

The study included some control variables such as foreign direct investment and trade openness. Therefore the model is given as:

$$Y = f(\text{GFC}, \text{LFP}, \text{OR}, \text{NOR}, \text{PRE}, \text{PCE}, \text{PDD}, \text{PED}, \text{FDI}, \text{TO}) \tag{3}$$

The study employed an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. The short run model used when there is no cointegration among the variables is presented in equation (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln INDO_t = & \alpha_{01} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_{01i} \Delta \ln INDO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{1i} \Delta GFC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{2i} \Delta LFP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln OR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln NOR_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{5i} \Delta \ln PRE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{6i} \Delta \ln PCE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{7i} \Delta \ln PDD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{8i} \Delta \ln PED_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{9i} \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{10i} \Delta TO_{t-i} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The long run model used when there is cointegration is the error correction model presented in equation (5) where the error correction term represents all the long run components with lambda (λ) as the coefficient.

$$\Delta \ln INDO_t = \alpha_{01} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_{01} \Delta \ln INDO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{1i} \Delta GFC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{2i} \Delta LFP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{3i} \Delta \ln OR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{4i} \Delta \ln NOR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{5i} \Delta \ln PRE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{6i} \Delta \ln PCE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{7i} \Delta \ln PDD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{8i} \Delta \ln PED_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{9i} \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \beta_{10i} \Delta TO_{t-i} + \lambda ECT_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (5)$$

Where:

- INDO = Industrial sector output
- GFC = Gross fixed capital formation
- LFP = Labour force participation rate
- OR = Oil revenue
- NOR = Non-oil revenue
- PRE = Public recurrent expenditure
- PCE = Public capital expenditure
- PDD = Public domestic debt
- PED = Public external debt
- FDI = Foreign direct investment
- TO = Trade openness
- ln = natural logarithm
- ECT_{t-1} = Error correction term

Based on Solow (1956), gross fixed capital formation and labour force participation rate are expected to have a positive effect on output growth. Investment in new capital goods and technology can lead to improved productivity, enabling businesses to produce more with the same amount of labour and resources. Fiscal policy variables such as public revenue, public capital expenditures and public debt are expected to have a positive effect because as government revenue increases and it correspondingly increases public capital expenditure, income in the hands of individuals would also increase thereby increasing output production activities. Trade openness is expected to have a positive effect on sectoral output as in Neoh and Lai (2021), Kpagih *et al.* (2022) and Tahir *et al.* (2019). This is possible when the bulk of foreign trade are exported goods that were produced domestically. FDI is also expected to have a positive effect on sectoral output because goods produced by such foreign investors within the country contribute to increasing the total GDP. However, it was insignificant in studies such as Eze *et al.* (2019), Obi *et al.* (2020) and Oyediran and Olajide (2024). There is need for further confirmation using recent data.

Data for this study cover the period from 1985 to 2023. Data for agricultural sector output, industrial sector output and service sector output, oil revenue, non-oil revenue, public capital expenditure, public recurrent expenditure, public domestic debt and public external debt were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2023). Foreign direct investment, trade openness, labour force participation rate and gross fixed capital formation were obtained from the World Development Indicators (2023).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the data used in this study is presented in Table 1. The mean value of industrial sector output is 13115.06 with a standard deviation of 203.594. The minimum value is 9845.947 and the maximum value is 16742.15. The mean and standard deviation of other variables are also presented.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Industrial sector output	Gross fixed capital formation	Labour force participation rate	Oil revenue
Mean	13115.08	2.82015	59.41461	3319.305
Median	13246.85	2.573367	60.24900	3592.448
Maximum	16742.15	40.3866	60.71200	8878.970
Minimum	9845.974	-23.74670	55.27000	71.88710
Std. Dev.	2083.594	11.29963	1.515558	2589.795
Kurtosis	1.677652	5.821932	3.548672	1.985821
Obs	34	34	34	34

Source: Authors' compilation (2025)

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics (continued)

Variables	Nonoil Revenue	Public recurrent expenditure	Public capital expenditure	Public domestic debt	Public external Debt	Trade openness
Mean	2172.956	2903.022	887.563	6546.909	4445.383	34.287
Median	1024.850	1489.735	603.0045	1961.448	1509.416	35.258
Maximum	13587.50	14287.56	4486.206	53258.01	38219.5	53.278
Minimum	18.325	36.2196	24.046	84.093	298.614	0.000
Std. Dev.	2920.229	3486.604	977.016	10251.53	7481.416	11.704
Kurtosis	8.610	5.170	7.156	13.802	13.638	3.486
Obs	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Authors' compilation (2025)

4.2 Unit Root Test

The unit root test was conducted using the Phillips-Perron test and the result is presented in Table 2. The results showed that gross fixed capital formation, log of oil revenue, log of public recurrent expenditure, foreign direct investment and trade openness are integrated of order zero while the log of industrial sector output, labour force participation rate, log of non-oil revenue, log of public capital expenditure and log of public external debt are integrated of order one. This implies that there is a mixed order of integration.

Table 2 Phillips-Perron Unit Root Test Result

Variable	Level			First Difference			Order of Integration
	Intercept	Trend and Intercept	None	Intercept	Trend and Intercept	None	
Log (INDO)	-0.969 (0.7527)	-1.703 (0.7271)	0.837 (0.8871)	-4.706 (0.0007)	-	-	I (1)
GFC	-7.219 (0.0000)	-	-	-	-	-	I(0)
LFP	-1.402 (0.5695)	-1.775 (0.6940)	-0.494 (0.4946)	-3.312 (0.0227)	-	-	I(1)

Log(OR)	-4.994 (0.0003)	-	-	-	-	-	I(0)
Log(NOR)	-1.053 (0.7222)	-1.967 (0.5973)	3.689 (0.9998)	-7.469 (0.0000)	-	-	I(1)
Log(PRE)	-3.376 (0.0193)	-	-	-	-	-	I(0)
Log(PCE)	-1.605 (0.4691)	-2.528 (0.3134)	2.457 (0.9956)	-6.616 (0.0000)	-	-	I(1)
Log(PDD)	-0.517 (0.8754)	-2.999 (0.1476)	5.292 (1.0000)	-2.230 (0.2001)	-1.649 (0.7501)	-0.543 (0.4737)	-
Log(PED)	-0.483 (0.8821)	-1.3333 (0.8617)	1.515 (0.9652)	-3.880 (0.0057)	-	-	I(1)
FDI	-0.350 (0.0127)	-	-	-	-	-	I(0)
TO	-3.023 (0.0430)	-	-	-	-	-	I(0)

Source: Authors' compilation (2025)

4.3 Lag Length Selection Criteria

This study conducted the lag length selection test using two criteria, which are the Akaike information criteria and the Schwarz information criteria. Basic on both criteria, the optimal lag length used in this study is 2. The results are presented in table 3,

Table 3 Lag Length Selection for the Industrial Sector Output Model

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-337.6287	NA	0.001292	21.72679	22.18484	21.87862
1	-116.5772	290.1301	8.95e-07	14.16107	19.19954	15.83118
2	135.7801	173.4957*	6.58e-10*	4.638742*	14.25763*	7.827133*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

4.4 Cointegration Test

Based on the mixed order of integration, the study employed the bound cointegration test. The result showed that the F-statistic is 4.698 which is greater than the lower and upper bound critical value of 2.65 and 3.97 at 1% significance level. This means that there is cointegration among the variables. The result is presented in table 4 below.

Table 4 Bounds Cointegration Test Result for the Industrial Sector Output Model

Test statistic	Significance	Lower Bound Critical Value I(0)	Upper Bound Critical Value I(1)
F-Statistic = 4.697871	10%	1.88	2.99
	5%	2.14	3.3
	2.5%	2.37	3.6
	1%	2.65	3.97

The estimation method employed in this study is the ARDL estimation method since there was a mixed order of integration and a long run relationships among the variables. The study therefore estimated an error correction model and the results are presented in Table 5 below.

4.5 Effect of Fiscal Policy on Industrial Sector Output

The results obtained showed that in the short run, the first difference of the first lag of the log of industrial sector output had a positive effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. However it was not significant.

The first difference of gross fixed capital formation had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. Therefore an increase in gross fixed capital formation significantly reduced the output from the industrial sector in the current year by 0.4403 percent showing a negative elasticity.

The first difference of the first lag of the log of gross fixed capital formation also had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that an increase in previous year's gross fixed capital formation caused a significant decline in the log of industrial sector output in the current year by 0.0042 percent. This shows a negative elasticity.

The first difference of the labour force participation rate had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that despite an increase in labour force participation rate the log of industrial sector output in the current year still declined significantly by 0.0642 percent showing a negative elasticity.

The first difference of the log of oil revenue had a negative effect on the the log of industrial sector output in the current year. However it was not significant. The first difference of the first lag of the log of oil revenue had a positive and significant effect on the the log of industrial sector output in the current year. Thus a one percent increase in the first lag of the log of oil revenue significantly improved the log of industrial sector output in the current year by 0.3519 percent implying a positive elasticity.

The first difference of the log of non-oil revenue had a negative and significant effect on log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that an increase in the log of non oil revenue significantly reduced the log of industrial sector output in the current year by 0.7044 percent showing a positive elasticity. The first difference of the first lag of the log of non oil revenue had a negative and significant effect on the the log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that a one an increase in the first lag of the log of non oil revenue significantly reduce the log of industrial sector output in the current year by 0.2254 showing a negative elasticity. Therefore despite the growth of nor oil revenue it did not significantly contribute to increasing output of the industrial sector.

The first difference of the log of public recurrent expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the the log of industrial sector output in the current year with a positive elasticity of 0.2297 percent.

The first difference of the first lag of the log of public recurrent expenditure had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year with a negative elasticity of 0.6715 percent. Therefore previous year's output performance significantly determines current year output.

The first difference of the log of public capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that a one percent increase in the log of public capital expenditure significantly reduced the log of industrial sector output in the recurrent year with a negative elasticity of 0.1952 percent.

The first difference of the first lag of the log of public capital expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year with an elasticity of 0.0690. Therefore although current year public capital expenditure had a negative reduction effect, the previous year's public capital expenditure had a significant increasing effect on industrial sector output. The first difference of the log of public external debt had a negative effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. However it was not significant.

The first difference of the first lag of the log of public external debt had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. This implies that a one percent increase in the lag of the log of public external debt significantly reduced the log of industrial sector output in the recurrent year by 0.0384 percent showing a negative elasticity. The first difference of foreign direct investment had a positive effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year. However it was not significant.

The first difference of the first lag of foreign direct investment had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year with an elasticity of 0.0983 percent. Therefore although current year foreign direct investment had an insignificant effect the previous year's foreign direct investment had a significant increasing effect.

The first difference of trade openness had a positive and significant effect on the the log of industrial sector output in the current year with an elasticity of 0.0018 percent. The first difference of the first lag of trade openness had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output in the current year with an elasticity of 0.0035 percent. Therefore although previous year trade openness had a negative effect, the effect of trade openness in the current year became positive.

In the long run, the results showed that the lag of oil revenue had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. This implies that a one percent in the log of oil revenue significantly improved the log of industrial sector output by 0.2159 percent showing a positive elasticity.

Labour force participation rate, the log of non-oil revenue, the log of public recurrent expenditure and the log of public capital expenditure were not significant.

Foreign direct investment had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output, while trade openness had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output.

Diagnostics and Post Estimation Results

Based on Table 6, the adjusted R-squared is 0.9090 which showed that there is high explanatory power of the model at 91 percent. The F-statistic of 17.3156 is highly significant showing that the overall model is significant or all the independent variables have a joint significant effect on the dependent variable. The result of the Normality test showed that the Jarque -Bara statistic is 0.8790 and it is not significant at five percent. Therefore we do not reject the null hypothesis which state that there is normality. This implies that there is normality in the model. The Breusch Godfrey serial correlation F-statistic of 10.6831 is not significant at five percent. Therefore we do not reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no serial correlation. This implies that there is no serial correlation. The F-statistic for hetroskedasticity is 11.1731 which is significant at 5%. Therefore we reject the null hypothesis which states there is no heteroskedesticity. This implies that the problem of heteroskedesticity is present.

The linearity test was conducted using the Ramsey Reset test method and the F-statistic is 0.3442 which is not significant at 5%. Therefore we do not reject the null hypothesis which states that there is linearity. This implies that the model is linear. The CUSUM stability test showed that there is stability

Table 5 Results for Industrial Sector Output Model

Short Run Estimates			
Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic	Probability
C	36.2829*	10.5445	0.0018
D(LOG INDO(-1))	0.4403	2.8474	0.0652
D(GFC)	-0.0015**	-4.8689	0.0166
D(GFC(-1))	-0.0042*	-8.4657	0.0035
D(LFP)	-0.0642*	-8.5367	0.0034
D(LOG \OR)	-0.0367	2.4474	0.0919
D(LOG OR(-1))	0.3519*	10.1930	0.0020
D(LOG NOR)	-0.7044*	-11.1472	0.0015
D(LOG NOR(-1))	-0.2254*	-8.7859	0.0031
D(LOG PRE)	0.2297**	5.8317	0.0100
D(LOG PRE(-1))	-0.6715*	-11.2757	0.0015
D(LOG PCE)	-0.1952*	-9.1579	0.0028
D(LOG PCE(-1))	0.0690**	4.9626	0.0157
D(LOG PED)	-0.0384	-3.0583	0.0551
D(LOG PED(-1))	-0.1110*	-7.9048	0.0047
D(FDI)	0.0548	2.2568	0.1093
D(FDI(-1))	0.0983**	4.8337	0.0169
D(TO)	0.0018**	4.8758	0.0165
D(TO(-1))	-0.0035*	-7.9951	0.0041
ECT(-1)	-3.2656*	-10.5315	0.0018

Long Run Estimates			
Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic	Probability
LFP	-0.0134	-1.2695	0.2236
LOG(OR)	0.2159**	2.8444	0.0123
LOG (NOR)	0.1139	-1.6957	0.1106
LOG (PRE)	-0.2418	-1.8646	0.0819
LOG (PCE)	0.0282	0.6224	0.5431
LOG (PED)	0.0533	1.6952	0.1107
FDI	0.5449**	2.8170	0.0130
TO	-0.0045**	-2.6938	0.0167

* and ** denote significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Table 6 Diagnostics and Post Estimation Test

Adjusted R-Squared = 0.9090	Breusch Godfrey Serial Correlation F-Statistic = 10.6831 (0.2114)
F-Statistic =17.3156 (0.000006)	Heteroskedasticity (ARCH) F -Statistic =11.1731 (0.0023)
Normality (Jarque - Bera) = 0.8790(0.644354)	Linearity (Ramsey Reset) F -Statistic= 0.3442 (0.6168)

Stability test (Cusum test)

4.6 Weighted Least Square Estimates

In order to correct for the presence of heteroskedasticity, the study employed the weighted least square estimation method. The weighted least squares help to solve the problem of heteroskedasticity by giving more weights to lower variance observations. It uses weights that are inversely proportional to the error variance. The study therefore employed this estimation method and the diagnostic test revealed the absence of the heteroskedasticity bias thereafter. The results are presented in Table 7.

Labour force participation rate had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. This implies that despite the increase in labour force participation rate the log of industrial sector output still declined significantly with an elasticity of 0.0072 percent.

The log of public recurrent expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. This implies that a one percent increase in the log of public recurrent expenditure significantly improved the log of industrial sector output by 0.0293.

The log of public capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. This implies that despite the increase in the log of public capital expenditure, it significantly reduced the log of industrial sector output by 0.0130 percent showing a negative elasticity. The log of oil revenue, the log of non-oil revenue, log of public external debt, gross fixed capital formation, foreign direct investment and trade openness were not significant.

Diagnostics and Post Estimation Results

The adjusted R-squared is 0.8155 which showed that there is a high explanatory power of the model at 82 percent. The F-statistic of 17.20220 is highly significant showing that the overall model is significant or all the independent variables have a joint significant effect on the dependent variable. The F-statistic for heteroskedasticity is 0.2050 which is not significant at five percent. Therefore the null hypothesis, which states there is no heteroskedasticity was not rejected. The result is presented in Table 8.

Table 7 Weighted Least Square Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic	Probability
GFC	-0.0009	-1.0370	0.3101
LFP	-0.0277	-2.9361	0.0073
LOG(OR)	0.0301	1.0705	0.2951
LOG(NOR)	-0.0033	-0.0642	0.9493
LOG(PRE)	0.1216	2.3182	0.0293
LOG(PCE)	-0.0884	-2.6845	0.0130
LOG (PED)	-0.0203	-1.4860	0.1503
FDI	-0.0215	-0.3390	0.7376
TO	-0.0007	-0.6055	0.5505
C	10.7872	-19.7872	0.0000

Table 8 Diagnostics and Post Estimation Test

Adjusted R-Squared = 0.8155	Heteroskedasticity (ARCH) F -Statistic =0.2050(0.6539)
F-Statistic =17.20220 (0.000000)	

4.7 Discussion of Results

Effect of Fiscal Policy on Industrial Sector Output

Gross fixed capital formation had a negative effect on the log of industrial sector output but it was not significant. This is possible when despite the increase in investment, such investment activities are not mostly in the industrial subsectors such as manufacturing, mining and quarrying, electricity, gas, steam and air conditioner etc. The result is similar to Yalah and Ogoun (2023) but contrary to Omankhanlen *et al.* (2021).

The result showed that despite the increase in labour force participation rate the log of industrial sector output still significantly declined. This negative effect may be due to the fact that a substantial number of the labour force are underemployed and not productive especially if they do not have the necessary skills, equipment and infrastructure.

The log of oil revenue had a positive effect on the log of industrial sector output but it was not significant. The log of non-oil revenue had a negative but insignificant effect on the log of agricultural sector output.

The log of public recurrent expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. This is similar to Oshota (2023), Aiyedogbon *et al* (2023), Joshua-Gyang (2024) but it is contrary to Effiong *et al* (2024), Victor and Romasn (2017).

The log of public capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect on the log of industrial sector output. Therefore despite the increase in government expenditure on capital projects and infrastructures, output from the industrial sector still declined. This is possible when the amount of capital spending by the government is not substantial enough to be able to provide an enabling environment that increases the ease of doing business and reduces the cost of production for investors. For instance, when the government makes insubstantial expenditures such as providing scanty or poor power and water supply. This increases the production cost of investors who have to source for these resources themselves thus discouraging investment. When development is not evenly distributed so that industrial investors have easy access to infrastructural resources in whichever area of the country that they choose to cite their firm, it would also deter industrial production. For instance, expenditures on roads and bridges may not necessarily improve industrial sector output when such roads are mostly in urban areas and cities while rural areas and farmlands lack good access to roads. Having good roads would enhance easy movement around farms during planting and

distribution of harvested farm products to the market and these products are important resources for the manufacturing sector. The result is similar to Effiong *et al.* (2024) but contrary to Victor and Roman (2017) and Oshota (2023).

The log of public external debt had a negative but insignificant effect on the log of industrial sector output. The insignificant effect could be as a result of not directing these borrowed funds towards sustainable investment activities in the manufacturing, construction, electricity, gas, steam and air conditioner among other subsectors. This is similar to Mohammed (2024) and Joshua-Gyang (2024).

Foreign direct investment had a negative but insignificant effect on the log of industrial sector output. Despite the increase in FDI, it may become insignificant when majority of such investments are not situated in the industrial sector. This is similar to Oyediran and Olajide (2024) but contrary to Ullah *et al.* (2012).

Trade openness had a negative effect on the log of industrial sector output. However it was not significant. This is contrary to Neoh and Lai (2021), Tahir *et al.* (2019), Umoh and Effiong (2013). This is possible when a country's trade openness encourages more of import than export. Local manufacturing of goods will decline when the market is flooded with imported goods and the demand for such goods is high. The lack of export incentives for company can discourage local production. Therefore a country's strategies for ensuring trade openness should encourage exports more than imports.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that only the public expenditure component of fiscal policy significantly determined industrial sector output and although public recurrent expenditure had a positive effect, public capital expenditure had a reduction effect. Therefore, government consumption spendings in the form of recurrent expenditure should patronize domestically produced goods in order to encourage more local industry production thereby sustaining the positive effect. Public capital expenditure should intentionally provide the basic infrastructures that reduce the cost of doing business in order to encourage industrial sector investment. For instance, the provision of basic infrastructures such as stable power supply and good road networks go a long way to reduce the production cost and attract investors.

Public revenue and public external debt were not significant. Therefore there is the need to substantially increase the proportion of revenue and debts specifically used by the government to create an enabling environment and provide the necessary infrastructures required for investors in the industrial sector to thrive and expand. Using public revenue and public debts to finance the provision of functional airports and shipping ports, good road networks, and transportation facilities help to increase industrial sector activities and output. Labour force participation rate also significantly determined output from the industrial sector. Trade openness, gross fixed capital formation and foreign direct investment were insignificant.

REFERENCES

- Abodunrin, I. A., Omitogun, O. & Onanuga, A. T. (2024). Fiscal deficit and economic performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 108-120.
- Acikgoz, B. & Cinar, S. (2017). Public spending and economic growth: an empirical analysis of developed countries. *Ekonomicky Casopis* 65: 448-458.
- Aghion, P., Hemous, D., & Kharroubi, E. (2014). Cyclical fiscal policy, credit constraints, and industry growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 62, 41-58.

- Aiyedogbon, J. O., Olorunfemi, G. M., & Ezie, O., (2023). The effect of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 3(4), 11-28.
- Arikpo, O. F., Ogar, A., & Ojong, C. M. (2017). The impact of fiscal policy on the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *Euro-Asian Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(1), 11-22.
- Central Bank of Nigeria Economic Report (2024). Central Bank of Nigeria.
- Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2024). Central Bank of Nigeria
- Choi, J., & Son, M. (2016) A note on the effects of government spending on economic growth in Korea. *Journal of Asia Pacific Economics* 21: 651–663.
- Easterly, W. & Rebelo, S. (1993). Fiscal policy and economic growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 32, 417- 458.
- Effiong, U. E., Ukere, I. J., & Ekpe, J. P. (2024). Fiscal policy, interest rate and the manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 2514-2533.
- Eller, M., Fidrmuc, J., & Fungáčová, Z. (2016). Fiscal policy and regional output volatility: Evidence from Russia. *Regional Studies*, 50(11), 1849-1862.
- Eze, A.A., Nnaji, M., & Nkalu, C.N. (2019). Impact of foreign direct investment on manufacturing sector output growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting*, 5(2) 55-64.
- Eze, O. R. (2014) Impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *British Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(2), 31-54.
- Falade, O. E., & Oladiran, O. I. (2015). Effect of government capital expenditure on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *Business and Economic Research*, 5(2), 136-152.
- Harrod, R. F. (1939). An essay in dynamic theory. *The Economic Journal*, 49:14–33.
- Ighoroje, E. J., and Akpokerere, O. E. (2021). Fiscal policy and industrial sector output in Nigeria. *Quest Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 9(1), 42-49.
- Imide, I. O. (2019). Empirical review of the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy (1980- 2017), *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 10(2), 89 – 97.
- Joshua-Gyang, E. (2024). Impact of fiscal policy indicators on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Tourism, Environment and Social Sciences* 3(1).
- Kpagih, L., Amadi, C. R., & Ezeunwo, N. (2022). External sector and performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 5(1), 78-90.
- Mohammed, S. R. (2024). The effect of public debt and government expenditure on industrial sector performance. *Journal of Business Development and Management Research*, 5(7). 223-234.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). *Sectoral Contribution to GDP in Nigeria*.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2023). Nigeria’s National Development Plan 2021-2025: Progress and Review.
- Neoh, N. S. & Lai, S. T. (2021). The impact of trade openness on manufacturing sector performance: evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Economics and Sustainability*, 3(1), 12-22.
- Nwanne, T. F. I. (2015). Implications of government capital expenditure on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 3(10), 19-33.
- Ogu, C., & Kem, P. O. (2020). Impact of taxation on industrial performance in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 18(1), 173 – 185.

- Oladipo, A. O., Joshua, B. Y., Machi, I. O., Yusuf, A. M., & Afamefuna, M. E. (2023). Fiscal policy and industrial sector development in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research (JEAR)*, 8(4), 66-78.
- Olaniyi, O. A., Adekanmbi, A. M., & Alabi, M. O. (2024). Exploring the causal nexus between tax composition, infrastructure and economic performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 98-107.
- Olawale, B. V., Ijirshar, V. U., Tersugh, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Impact of government fiscal expansion on manufacturing output in Nigeria. *Card International Journal of Management Studies, Business & Entrepreneurship Research*, 2(2), 198-214.
- Omankhanlen, A. E., Chimezie, P. O., & Lawrence, O. U. (2021). Impact of government expenditure on sustainable industrial development in Nigeria. *WSEAS Transaction on Business and Economics*, 8(4), 31-41.
- Osabuohien, E., & Ike, F. (2023). Macroeconomic policy challenges and structural reforms in Nigeria. *Economic Policy Review*, 47(3), 90–103.
- Oshota, S. O. (2023). Fiscal policy and sectoral output growth in Nigeria: a new empirical evidence. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 8(3), 18-34.
- Oyediran, A. A. & Olajide, L. E. (2024). Foreign direct investment and macroeconomic dynamics in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 17-28.
- Ozuzu, S., & Isukul, A. (2021). Government expenditure and its effect on the industrial sector in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 21(7), 81-92.
- Popiel, M. K. (2020). Fiscal policy uncertainty and US output. *Studies in Nonlinear Dynamics & Econometrics*, 24(2), 20180024.
- Solow, R. (1956). A contribution to the theory of economic growth, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 70(1):65–94.
- Tahir, M., Mazhar, T., & Afridi, M. A. (2019). Trade openness and sectoral growth in developing countries: some new insights. *Journal of Chinese Economic and Foreign Trade Studies*, 12(2), 90-103.
- Tkalec, M. & Vizek, M. (2009). The impact of macroeconomic policies on manufacturing production in Croatia, *Privredna Kretanja I Ekonomska Politika*. 121, 61-92.
- Uffie, E. J. & Aghanenu, A. S. (2019). Fiscal policy and manufacturing sector output: the Nigerian evidence. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 9(7), 13 – 25.
- Umoh, J. O. & Effiong, L. E. (2013). Trade openness and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. *The Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 7: 147. DOI: 10.1177/0973801013483505
- Victor, S. & Roman, K. (2017). Modeling of fiscal policy effects on agriculture and industry in Ukraine. *Journal of Information System in Management*, 6(2): 131-142
- Yalah. B. & Ogoun, S. (2023). Gross fixed capital formation and industrial development in Nigeria. *UBS Journal of Business and Economic Policy*, 1(4), 134 – 144.
- Zagler, M., & Dürnecker, G. (2003). Fiscal policy and economic growth. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 17(3), 397-418.